

COGNITIVE METAPHOR IN THE FRAMEWORK OF MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract.

The article is aimed to study "cognitive metaphor theory" and define the difference between cognitive and traditional metaphor, as well as discuss types of cognitive metaphor.

Key words.

cognitive metaphor, concept, mental spaces, conceptual features, conceptualization.

Introduction

From a traditional point of view, metaphor is defined as a trope consisting in the use of a word that denotes a certain class of objects, phenomena, actions or signs to designate another, similar to the given, class of objects, projects or individuals. For example: *Laughter is the best medicine; Words are daggers when spoken in anger; His words are pearls of wisdom.* It should be mentioned that Aristotle was the first to study the essence of metaphor. He believed that metaphors are hidden comparisons based on the principle of analogy. He also convinced that metaphor serves as an ornament to speech and is a kind of literary device.

Main part

With the development of cognitive linguistics, the notion of metaphor has been rethought. Linguists have introduced a new notion, the notion of "cognitive metaphor" also acknowledged as "conceptual metaphor".

The founders of the theory of cognitive metaphor are George Lakoff and Mark Johnson. They present metaphor as a structure that defines how we perceive the world, think and what we do. Linguists claim that we cognize and perceive the world around us with the help of cognitive metaphors, even without realizing it. We perceive metaphorically almost everything around us: people, situations, time, place, etc.

The essence of the theory of conceptual metaphor is that the conceptual metaphor can be considered as a cognitive mechanism consisting of two mental spaces: the source-domain and the target-domain. Following Lavrova N.A., under the mental space we understand "the totality of linguistic and non-linguistic

knowledge stored in long-term memory and reflecting a person's ideas about objects and objects of reality that arise as a result of the process of cognition of the world based on sensory-motor, cultural-social and individual experience" [2015: 296].

In other words, the mental space is a concept. In the process of interaction of two mental spaces (two concepts), the conceptual features of the source space are projected onto the target space, as a result of which the target space acquires a new meaning. One of well-known examples in the theory of conceptual metaphor is the metaphor "Love is death". In this example, the concept "death" belongs to the source space, and the concept "love" belongs to the target space. As a result of the interaction of two spaces, the concept of "love" takes on a new meaning, which is "a strong feeling of admiration that makes a person mad and cruel, so as he/she can kill another person". It should be emphasized that in most of the analyzed examples of conceptual metaphor, more abstract concepts refer to the source space, and objects of reality refer to the target space. Therefore, the source space may include:

- specific objects (plants, money, liquid, food);
- body parts, animals and senses;
- activity and movement;
- place and space.

Source space may include:

- spiritual values, quality and quantity;
- emotions, experiences and relationships;
- thoughts and speech;
- feelings;
- substances.

From the information mentioned above, it should be emphasized that one of the main functions of a cognitive metaphor is not only the creation of a new meaning, but also the explanation of an existing meaning. A cognitive metaphor is used to form an example of an unknown conceptual area with the help of a more familiar concept or phenomenon. According to Lakoff and Johnson, metaphor is one of the important tools for explaining something partially that is impossible or difficult to explain completely. Thus, cognitive metaphor also serves to categorize objects and phenomena of reality.

As Lavrova N.A. notes, categorization involves summing up the diversity of human experience under certain groups and categories, as well as the distribution of information coming to the senses into rubrics, united by a commonality of signs

and characteristics. When perceiving a specific object for which there is already a category, it is not difficult for a person to correlate this new object with the existing category, provided that the object has all the necessary features and features of this category. So, when faced with an unfamiliar breed of dog, a child, as a rule, unmistakably categorizes this breed as dogs, not cats or birds.

It should also be noted that in the work "Metaphors We Live By" George Lakoff and Mark Johnson distinguish several types of cognitive metaphor, the main of which are structural, orientational and ontological metaphors. Let us take a look at each of these types below.

Structural metaphor is a kind of metaphor when one complex concept (abstract) is represented by another (more specific) concept. For example: *argument is war, time is money*.

Oriental metaphor is a metaphor based on spatial orientation. At the same time, the positive concept is most often oriented upward, and the negative concept is oriented downward. Well-known examples of orientational metaphor are: *happy is up, sad is down, conscious is up, unconscious is down*.

An ontological metaphor serves different purposes (experience, state, evaluation, quantity, etc.). Well-known examples of ontological metaphor are: *inflation is lowering our standard of living; my cell phone died on me*.

The following scientists also devoted their studies to the study of cognitive metaphor: Black M. V., Richards A., Kubryakova E. S., Demyankov V. Z., Budaev E. V., Ashurova D. U. and others. Black M. V., defines metaphor as a filter in a system of generally accepted associations. He is the founder of "interactionist theory", the essence of which is similar to the theory of cognitive metaphor. Black identifies two subjects in the metaphor: the main subject (principal subject) and the auxiliary subject (subsidiary subject). Its well-known example is the "Man is a wolf" metaphor.

According to Kubryakova E.S., a cognitive metaphor is defined as "one of the forms of conceptualization, a cognitive process that expresses and forms new concepts and without which it is impossible to obtain new knowledge." In her work, she notes that "metaphor usually refers not to individual isolated objects, but to complex mental spaces (areas of sensory or social experience).

In the processes of cognition, these complex, directly unobservable mental spaces are correlated through a metaphor with simpler or specifically observable mental spaces (for example, human emotions are compared with fire, the spheres of economics and politics are compared with games, sports competitions, etc.).

Arutyunova N.D., notes that cognitive metaphor is the ability of a person to capture and create similarities between different individuals and classes of objects [1990: 15]. In the most general approach, cognitive metaphor is a vision of one object through another and in this sense is one of the ways representation of knowledge in linguistic form.

Budaev E.V. defines cognitive metaphor as "a mental operation, as a way of knowing, categorizing, conceptualizing, evaluating and explaining the world" [2007:17]. At the same time, the linguist emphasizes that the cognitive metaphor plays an important role in the categorization of the surrounding reality, which is one of the main problems of cognitive linguistics in general.

According to Ashurova D.U., cognitive metaphor is one of the fundamental processes of human cognition, contributes to the conceptualization of reality, based on the mental process of analogy and the transfer of knowledge from one conceptual space to another [2016].

Conclusion

It should be emphasized that the role of cognitive metaphor in the interpretation of a literary text is especially great, as it helps the reader to penetrate into the deep semantics of the text and understand the author's intention.

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